

Differences in root volume of selected upland and lowland rice varieties

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Refined selection techniques that offer greater precision in screening for drought resistance are needed to assess the avoidance and tolerance mechanisms that operate at different growth stages.

High root volume indicates that a plant can permeate a large volume of soil or that it has a high proportion of thick roots. Theoretically, such a plant would have greater water-gathering potential for growth and survival.

We investigated differences in root volume among upland and lowland rice varieties and compared aboveground characters that might be associated with high root volume.

Thirteen test varieties identified in mass field screening to have varying reactions to drought were grown in an aeroponic culture system. The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Root volume was determined by displacement of water in a 1-liter graduated cylinder 44 d after seed soaking. Other root and shoot characters also were measured.

Test varieties differed appreciably in root volume. Rikuto Norin 21, a Japanese upland variety, had the greatest root volume; IR20, a semi-dwarf drought-susceptible lowland variety, the least (Table 1). Upland varieties in general had greater root

Table 1. Mean root volume of 13 rice varieties 44 d after seed soaking, and field reaction to drought. IRRRI, 1989.

Variety	Type of culture ^a	Mean volume ^b (ml)	Drought reaction ^c	
			Vegetative phase	Reproductive phase
Rikuto Norin	U	31 a	3	5
Kalakeri	U	30 ab	7	5
BPI-76	RL	26 abc	3	—
Moroberekan	U	23 a-d	5	3
Guang-Mao 127	RL	22 bcd	—	—
Dular	DP	21 cde	5	3
Kinandang Patong	U	21 cde	3	3
Salumpikit	U	16 def	4	6
Taichung Native 1	IL	15 def	6	9
Mahsuri	RL	14 def	5	9
Palawan	U	14 def	4	—
IR8	IL	13 ef	4	9
IR20	IL	10 f	7	9

^aU = upland, RL = rainfed lowland, IL = improved lowland, DP = dual purpose. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^c1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

volumes than lowland varieties. Among the lowland varieties, BPI-76 had a greater root volume than drought-resistant check Moroberekan. (BPI-76 was moderately resistant to field drought in upland mass screening nurseries.)

Root volume was negatively associated with reproductive phase drought reaction (-0.85**): varieties showing high drought resistance had greater root volumes than susceptible varieties.

Interactions among plant characters are important in determining appropriate indices to select for drought resistance. Associations between root volume and root or shoot characters were positive except for tiller number (Table 2). The only significant correlations, however, were between root volume and root length and between root volume and shoot length.

Table 2. Relationship between root volume and 7 root or shoot characters of 13 test varieties. IRRRI, 1989.

Character	<i>r</i>
Root volume vs	
Root length	0.86589**
Root diameter	0.43166 ^{ns}
Root number	0.11297 ^{ns}
Root/shoot ratio	0.48075 ^{ns}
Shoot length	0.68428**
Tiller number	-0.08742 ^{ns}
Leaf number	0.00738 ^{ns}

In earlier studies, root length was correlated positively with shoot length. Thus, tall plants should have deep roots and large root volumes. Plant height could then be a useful criterion for selecting progenies with deep root systems and high root volume, especially for resistance to drought during the reproductive phase. ■

Variation in chlorophyll content of rice flag leaf lamina and sheath

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The chlorophyll content of the lamina, sheath, and exposed internode indicates the photosynthetic potential of these organs. One may conceptualize a

rice ideotype whose enhanced photosynthetic potential of the flag leaf lamina, leaf sheath, exposed internode, and panicle allows significant reduction in the size of leaf blades, without reducing the plant's assimilatory potential. Such a plant type could be suitable for high density planting and high fertilizer N application.

In 1989 dry season, we studied variation in chlorophyll content of the flag leaf lamina and sheath of five rice

varieties of similar flowering duration (group 1). A chlorophyll meter (Minolta SPAD 502) was used to measure chlorophyll values at heading for flag leaf blade and sheath from the main culms of 10 plants/variety per three replications.

IR47686-6-2-2-1 had the highest chlorophyll content in the flag leaf blade (Table 1). Suweon 290 had the highest chlorophyll content in the sheath.

Table 1. Chlorophyll content of flag leaf blade and sheath at heading in 11 rice genotypes. IRRI, 1989 dry season.

Genotype	Chlorophyll content (mg/100 cm ^{2a})	
	Lamina	Sheath
Group I		
IR47686-6-2-2-1	3.9	1.6
IR29723-143-3-2-1	3.6	1.7
IR35686-56-2-2-2	3.4	1.7
Suweon 290	3.3	1.9
IR33043-46-1-3	3.1	1.5
Mean	3.5	1.7
SEM	0.1	0.1
Group II		
IR47705-Ac5	5.6	2.3
IR47705-Ac3-2	5.2	2.1
IR47705-Ac6	4.9	2.0
IR34615-75-1-1	4.6	2.4
IR47705-Ac5-1	4.2	2.7
IR28211-43-1-1-2	4.2	2.3
Mean	4.8	2.3
SEM	0.2	0.1

^aSPAD 502 reading converted to chlorophyll content $y = 0.0996r - 0.152$, where y = chlorophyll content and r = SPAD 502 reading.

Six additional lines, growing without replication in a different field, were selected for their dark green foliage (group 2). Their flag leaf blade and sheath chlorophyll values were higher than those for the first varieties studied. IR47705-Ac5 had the highest chlorophyll content in the lamina while IR47705-Ac5-1 had the highest content in the sheath.

In 1989 wet season, we screened 22 additional genotypes without replication. Genotype means were based on five culms each from separate, randomly selected hills. Acc. 2293 had 91% higher chlorophyll content in the lamina than Acc. 1525 (Table 2). Acc. 1214 had 81% higher chlorophyll content in the sheath than Acc. 1097. Evaluation of more lines would likely reveal even larger differences for these traits.

Nonsignificant correlations between lamina and sheath chlorophyll content for the two groups of genotypes during 1989 dry season and 22 genotypes during 1989 wet season indicate that it should be possible to develop recombinants having high chlorophyll content

in both lamina and sheath. Such recombinants are likely to have higher photosynthetic potential and, thus, higher yield potential.

Alternatively, high lamina and sheath chlorophyll contents could be

combined with reduced lamina area without loss of a plant's photosynthetic potential. Such a plant type could produce higher yields through more panicles/unit area under high density planting. □

Table 2. Chlorophyll content of flag leaf lamina and sheath at heading in 22 rice genotypes. IRRI, 1989 wet season.

Acc no.	Name	Origin	Chlorophyll content (mg/100 cm ²)	
			Lamina	Sheath
2293	Zi Talc	Korea	6.1	2.0
2286	Wase Shinsu	Korea	5.6	1.9
26168	Riuc V13	Brazil	5.5	2.0
3236	Coll 7393	Turkey	5.2	2.1
3197	Paraitalica Fiacco	Portugal	5.2	2.1
1179	Hung Chao Lu Hyu	China	4.7	2.1
1414	Tu Pien	China	4.7	1.9
2531	Coll 232	Japan	4.7	1.8
2575	Ishikari Shiraj	Japan	4.7	1.9
2622	Norin 11	Japan	4.6	1.7
2663	Shinao Mochi 3	Japan	4.6	1.8
9277	Fujisaka 3	Japan	4.6	2.1
61802	He Jiang 19	China	4.6	1.8
2511	Suito Norin	Japan	4.4	2.1
2627	Norin 28	Japan	4.4	2.1
3105	82	Italy	4.4	2.2
3123	Sancio P6 Tipo	Italy	4.4	2.0
1214	Dacca 345	China	3.7	2.9
8433	DNJ 133	Bangladesh	3.5	2.0
1097	Tawng 282	China	3.4	1.6
1588	K 184	China	3.4	1.6
1525	Tsu Ta Li	China	3.2	1.9
	Mean		4.5	2.0
	SEM		0.2	0.1

Biomass, grain yield, and harvest index of F₁ rice hybrids and inbreds

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Grain yield is the product of total dry matter (biomass) and harvest index (HI). Total dry weight measures the overall crop photosynthetic performance; HI is the ratio of biomass partitioned into grains. Significant heterosis for total dry matter and HI has been observed, and genetic manipulation to develop hybrids with higher biomass and HI merits consideration.

We evaluated the performance of 57 F₁ hybrids and 43 inbreds with growth

durations ranging from 110 to 138 d in an unreplicated irrigated field trial in 1988 dry season. Hybrids and inbreds were grouped according to maturity, with 5-d intervals for each group. Plots were fertilized basally with 80-13-25 kg NPK/ha and 40 kg N/ha was topdressed 6 wk after transplanting. Plant spacing was 20 × 20 cm with 1 seedling/hill. Total dry weight at maturity and grain yield were measured from 20 hills/variety.

Biomass production increased with growth duration (Fig. 1). Heterosis was observed for biomass and grain yield. F₁ hybrids showed almost 10% advantage in biomass and 20% advantage in grain yield over the high-yielding inbreds.

Regardless of growth duration, grain yield was almost the same except for a